

REPORT ON

FARM TRIALS TO SCREEN APPROPRIATE PULSE AND OILSEED VARIETIES SUITABLE FOR POST MONSOON SEASON IN CHHATTISGARH

VARITAL TRIAL ON FARMER'S FIELD NOVEMBER/DECEMBER 2020 TO MARCH/APRIL SEASON 2021

December, January, February and March Activities' Report WITH

- *Characterization of farmers' varieties*
- *Pulse germplasms characterized for climate adaptation*
- *Knowledge about Climate resilient varieties enhanced*

Submitted on 15 April 2021

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Under

FAO (ITPGR) BSF-IV Cycle Project for India on

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Acknowledgement

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Chhattisgarh Team - Shri Geet Sharma ji, Shri Pradeep Sharma, Shri Shailndera Tiwari and farmer community

Project Area

Chhattisgarh - District Bilaspur; Block Kota, Villages – Mandalpara, Kadampara, Piparpara. (~10 km²)

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A. SOWING PERIOD: November-December 2020 Reporting Month: November/December 2020

Annexure-1: Seed list (Farmers' variety); Seed collection during varietal trial plot design in November 2020.

Annexure -2: Chhattisgarh: Varietal Trial Plot Design for Post Monsoon Season, November 2020

There were sowed six farms (Trial Farm 1 to 6). Total 7 varieties of 6 crops are introduced in the late monsoon season. 1 varieties of Chana or Bengal Gram, 2 varieties of Black Mustard, 1 varieties of local pulse "Tiwara", 1 variety of Kulthi, 1 Variety of Masoor and 1 variety of Linseed/Alsi.

November/December 2020:

Sowing and Germination:

FARM NO.-1

Farmer – Rampad Markam
(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Reporting Date: 3/12/2020 | 10/12/2020

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली कालगना/Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination - soil moisture -Crack the soil – large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
2 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	03/12/2020	40	No			
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			
4 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	03/12/2020	60	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			
6 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	03/12/2020	60	No			

FARM NO.-2
Farmer – RAMPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Chana, Tiwara and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली का लगना / Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination - soil moisture -Crack the soil – large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig
2 Tiwara Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	50	No			Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
3 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	03/12/2020	40	No			
4 Tiwara Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			
6 Tiwara Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			
7 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	03/12/2020	50	No			

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FARM NO.-3
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARAKAM
(Crops: Chana, Kulthi and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली का लगना / Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali)	03/12/2020	50	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig

Haat/Manoj) 2 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Am- bikapur -Area	03/12/2020	50	No		- soil moisture -Crack the soil – large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Achanakmar Wild- life Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilas- pur), around 20 km distance.
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	60	No			
4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			
6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	50	No			
7 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Am- bikapur -Area	03/12/2020	40	No			

FARM NO.- 4
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली कालगना/Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	60	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination - soil moisture -Crack the soil – large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig
2 Mustard Chhattisgrah University Variety	03/12/2020	50	No			Achanakmar Wild- life Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilas-

3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			pur), around 20 km distance.
4 Mustard Chhattisgrah University Variety	03/12/2020	50	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			
6 Mustard Chhattisgrah University Variety	03/12/2020	50	No			
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			

FARM NO.- 5
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Chana and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली कालगना/Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination - soil moisture -Crack the soil - large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig
2 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			

4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No			
6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	03/12/2020	40	No			
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			

FARM NO.- 6
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Linseed (Alsi) and Chana)

Trial Plot No.	Sowing Date	% of Germination	Any pest attacked	Problem with monsoon water logging	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Yes Data required for scientist (50% फली कालगना/Yield etc.)	Other vulnerable factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	50	No	No	Yes -To check Seed germination - soil moisture -Crack the soil – large pieces into small or tiny pieces	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
2 Alsi Local Desi	03/12/2020	40	No			
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			
4 Alsi Local Desi	03/12/2020	50	No			
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	03/12/2020	40	No			
6	03/12/2020	40	No			

Alsi Local Desi						
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12 December: Germination

12 December: Germination

12 December: Germination

21 December: Linseed/Alsi

21 December: Chana

Relay cropping:

21 December 2021; Tiawara in Paddy Field

22 Jan 2021: Baturi; Relay Cropping

Number of Plants-stand and % Flowering:

JANUARY 2021:

FARM NO.-1
Farmer – Rampad Markam
(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower on date 22 Jan 2021	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N)Yes..... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिट्टी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	70	50	No	No	Yes -To check the need for the manure, Pesticides, -Check the Fruits, flower and insect	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
2 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	40	50	No	No		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	60	40	No	No		
4 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	40	50	No	No		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	60	40	No	No		
6 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	40	40	No	No		

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.. > .6...>.5..>.4...>.3 ..>.2...>.....>.....>.....>**Less growth**

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

A. 1).....1=3=5..... =2)==.....3)= ... (Crop Name: Chana)

B. 1).....2=4=6... =2)==.....3)= = (Crop Name: Mustard)

FARM NO.-2
Farmer – RAMPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Chana, Tiwara and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower on date 22 Jan 2021	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिट्टी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	60	60	No	No	Yes -To check the need for the manure, Pesticides, - Check the Fruits, flower and insect	Domestic Animal Like Cow, Bull, Forest-Deer; Wild Pig Achanakmar Wildlife Sanctuary near project site (kota block, district Bilaspur), around 20 km distance.
2 Tiwara Bachali Haat	50	40	No	No		
3 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	40	50	No	No		
4 Tiwara Bachali Haat	50	50	No	No		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	50	70	No	No		
6 Tiwara Bachali Haat	50	60	No	No		
7 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajha	40	40	No	No		

r Haat)						
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Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...2.. > .5.>. ...7.. >...1...>...3...>...4...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

- A. 1)....1=5...= ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Chana.)
- B. 1)....2=4=6 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Tiwara)
- C. 1)....3=7...= ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Mustard)

FARM NO.-3
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARAKAM
(Crops: Chana, Kulthi and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower on date 22 Jan 2021	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N)Yes..... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिटटी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	70	60	No	No	To check the flower	
2 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Ambika- pur -Area	40	40	No	No		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	70	50	No	No		
4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	40	60	No	No		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	60	40	No	No		

6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	40	50	No	No
7 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Ambika- pur -Area	40	55	No	No

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... > ..3.....>. ...2.. >.....5...>...6....>...4...>...7...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

B. 1)....1=3=5 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Chana)

C. 1)....2=7 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Kulthi)

D. 1)....4=6 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Masoor)

FARM NO.- 4

Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM

(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...Yes... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिटटी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	75	60	No	No	Yes	Cattle
2 Mustard Chhattis- grah University Variety	40	50				
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	40	50				
4 Mustard	50	55				

Chhattis- grah University Variety						
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	50	50				
6 Mustard Chhattis- grah University Variety	60	50				
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	60	50				

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... > ..2.....>. ...4.. >.....6...>...3....>...5...>...7.....Less growth

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

A. 1)....1=3=5=7... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Chana.)

B. 1)....2=4... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Mustard)

FARM NO.- 5
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Chana and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...Yes... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिटटी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	60	50	No			
2 Masoor Local Desi Bachali	40	40				

Haat						
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	40	50				
4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	40	60				
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	50	50				
6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	40	50				
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	40	40				

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... > ..3.....>.5.. >.....2...>...4....>...6...>...7...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with SAME/EQUAL farmers' varieties:

Group

A. 1)...1.=3=5=7 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Chana)

B. 1)...2.=4=6 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Mustard)

FARM NO.- 6
Farmer – RAMAPAD MARKAM
(Crops: Linseed (Aisi) and Chana)

Trial Plot No.	No. of plants Stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far पौधों में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना	Water logging बरसात के पानी का भराव	Contact with scientist (Y/N) ...Yes... Data required for scientist	other vulnerable factor अन्य प्रकार की कोई बात, जो नजर आयी, जैसे - पशु / termite/ भारी बरसात / मिटटी का कटाव/ उर्वरक /
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man	70	60	No	No	Yes	

oj) 2 Alsi Local Desi	40	50				
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	40	50				
4 Alsi Local Desi	50	60				
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Man oj)	40	50				
6 Alsi Local Desi	50	50				

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... > ..4.....>2... >.....3...>...5....>...6...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

A. 1)....1=3=5 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Chana)

B. 1)....2=4=6 ... =2).....==.....3)= (Crop Name: Alsi)

22 Jan 2021 : Chana

22 Jan 2021; Chana

22 Jan; Tiwara

22 Jan; Alsi (Linseed)

22 Jan; Mustard

Jan 22, 2021 4:59:06 PM

22 Jan; Tiwara

Jan 22, 2021 4:40:14 PM

22 Jan; Mustard

Jan 22, 2021 4:38:00 PM

22 Jan; Kulthi

22 Jan; Tiwara with flowering

22 Jan; Chana

22 Jan; Alsi

Pod and Harvesting:

Feb./MARCH 2021:

Farm No.-1: Varietal Trial at Farmer

Rampad Markam

(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	6-7	No	15/2/21 (Pre harvesting due to bad weather condition)	½ kg	-	Domestic Cattles
2 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	30/02/21	4-5	4-5		15/03/21	½ kg		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	5-7		15/2/21	1 kg		
4 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	30/02/21	4-5	3-5		15/03/21	500 gm		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	4-6		15/02/21	1 kg		
6 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	30/02/21	4-5	3-5		15/03/21	½ kg		

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...6.... >5..>. ...4...>...1...>...3....>...2...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with SAME/EQUAL farmers' varieties:

Group

E. 1)...1=3=5 ...2).....==.....3)= = (Crop Name: **Chana**)

B. 1)...2=4.....2)==.....3)= = ...(Crop Name: **Mustard**)

FARM NO.-2
Farmer -Rampad Markam

(Crops: Chana, Tiwara and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/ (फली लगनेकी दिनाक)	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant (प्रतिपौधेपर फली कीसंख्या)	Any disease observed in plants so far (पौधो मेंकोईबीमारी कादिखाईदेना)	Harvesting of pods (फलीकीतुड़ाईकी दिनाक)	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot (एकट्रायलप्लॉटमें कितना किलोफ लीनिकला)	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor (अन्यप्रकारकीकोईबात, जोनजरआयी, जैसे - पशु / Termite/ भारीबरसात / मिटटीकाकटाव)
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	7-5	No	15/02/21	½ kg	--	Domestic Cat-les
2 Tiwara Bachali Haat	15/02/21	3	7-8	No	30/02/21	½ kg		
3 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	30/02/21	4-5	4-5	No	15/03/21	½ kg		
4 Tiwara Bachali Haat	15/02/21	3	7-6	No	30/02/21	½ kg		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	5-6	No	15/02/21	½ kg		
6 Tiwara Bachali Haat	15/02/21	3	4-6	No	30/02/21	½ kg		
7 Mustard Giriraj (Bhaisajhar Haat)	30/02/21	4-5	5-6	No	15/03/21	400 gm		

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...2.... > ..5.....> ...7.. >...1.....>...3...>...4....>...Less growth

Similar Varieties:

- A) 1=5 Chana
- B) 2=4=6 Tiwara
- C) 3=7 Mustard

FARM NO.-3
Farmer – Rampad Markam
(Crops: Chana, kulthi and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/ (फली लगनेकी दिनांक)	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant (प्रतिपौधेपर फली कीसंख्या)	Any disease observed in plants so far (पौधो में कोई बीमारी का दिखाई देना)	Harvesting of pods (फलीकीतुड़ाईकी दिनांक)	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot (एक ट्रायल प्लाट में कितना किलो फली निकला)	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor (अन्यप्रकारकीकोईबात, जोनजरआयी, जैसे - पशु / Termite/ भारीबरसात / मिटटीकाकटाव)
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	5-6	No	15/02/21	½ kg	--	Domestic Cat- tles
2 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Ambikapur -Area	15/02/21	2-3	4-5		30/02/21	½ kg		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	4-5		15/02/21	400 gm		
4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	30/02/21	3-4	3-5		15/03/21	½ kg		
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	30/01/21	2	3-6		15/02/21	½ kg		
6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	30/02/21	2-3	3-5		15/03/21	½ kg		
7 Kulthi Local Sarguja/ Ambikapur	15/02/21	2-4	4-5		30/02/21	½ kg		

-Area							
-------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...3.... >1..>2... >...5.....>.....6...>...4...>...7...Less growth

2. Trial Farm with **SAME/EQUAL** farmers' varieties:

Group

F. 1)...1=3=5....2).....==.....3)= = (Crop Name : Chana)

B. 1)..2=7 ... =2)==.....3)= = (Crop Name: Kulthi)

C.1) ...4=6...2)==.....3)= = (Crop Name: Masoor)

FARM NO.- 4
Farmer -Rampad Mrakam
(Crops: Chana and Mustard)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/ (फली लगनेकीदिना क)	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant (प्रतिपौधेपर फली कीसं ख्या)	Any disease observed in plants so far (पौधो मेंकोईबीमारी कादिखाईदेना)	Harvesting of pods (फलीकीतुड़ाईकी दिनाक)	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot (एकटायलप्लाटमें कितना किलोफ लीनिकला)	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor (अन्यप्रकारकीकोईबात, जोनजरआयी, जैसे - पशु / Termite/ भारीबरसात / मिटटीकाकटाव)
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	No data recorded	2	5-6	No	No data recorded	½ kg	---	Cattles
2 Mustard Chhattisgrah University Variety	No data recorded	3-5	5-6		No data recorded	½ kg		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Manoj)	No data recorded	2	4-5		No data recorded	½ kg		
4 Mustard Chhattisgrah University Variety	No data recorded	3-5	5-6		No data recorded	½ kg		
5 Chana	No data recorded	2	4-5		No data recorded	½ kg		

Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)								
6 Mustard Chhattis grah Universi- ty Varie- ty	No data recorded	2	5-6		No data recorded	½ kg		
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	2	5-6		No data recorded	½ kg		

Note:

3. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... >2...>.4.. >..6....>...3..>...5..>..7.. Less growth

FARM NO.- 5
Farmer -Rampad Mrakam
(Crops: Chana and Masoor)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/ (फली लगनेकीदिना क)	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant (प्रतिपौधेपर फली कीसं ख्या)	Any disease observed in plants so far (पौधो मेंकोईबीमारी कादिखाईदेना)	Harvesting of pods (फलीकीतुड़ाईकी दिनाक)	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot (एकट्रायलप्लॉटमें कितना किलोफ लीनिकला)	Contact with scientist (Y) ...Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor (अन्यप्रकारकीकोईबात, जोनजरआयी, जैसे - पशु / Termite/ भारीबरसात / मिटटीकाकटाव)
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg	--	Cattles
2 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
4 Masoor Local Desi Bachali	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		

Haat								
5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
6 Masoor Local Desi Bachali Haat	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
7 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth ...1.... > ..4..>... 2.... >..3....>...5..>..6..Less growth

FARM NO.- 6

Farmer -Rampad Mrakam

(Crops: Chana and Alsi)

Trial Plot No.	Pod appearing date/ (फली लगनेकीदिना क)	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant (प्रतिपौधेपर फली कीसंख्या)	Any disease observed in plants so far (पौधो मेंकोईबीमारी कादिखाईदेना)	Harvesting of pods (फलीकीतुड़ाईकी दिनाक)	Quantity (kg)of pod got from trial plot (एकट्रायलप्लाटमें कितना किलोफ लीनिकला)	Contact with scientist (Y) ... Yes..... Data required for scientist	Other Vulnerable Factor (अन्यप्रकारकीकोईबात, जोनजरआयी, जैसे - पशु / Termite/ भारीबरसात / मिटटीकाकटाव)
1 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg	--	No
2 Alsi Local Desi	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
3 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
4 Alsi Local Desi	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		

5 Chana Kheri (Bachali Haat/Ma noj)	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		
6 Alsi Local Desi	No data recorded	-	-	-	No data recorded	½ kg		

Note:

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Mar 5, 2021 7:23:19 AM

5 March Baturi

Mar 5, 2021 7:23:07 AM

5 March Baturi

Mar 5, 2021 7:22:02 AM

5 March Baturi

Mar 5, 2021 7:16:32 AM

5 March 21: Chana

5 March 021: Masoor

05 March 2021: Chana

Overall summary:

Similar Varieties

Crop	Similar varieties			Similar varieties		Scientific Variety (S.V.)		Project Result	No. of Varieties
	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	Farmer Variety	S.V-1	S.V-2		
Black gram/ Chana			Kheri (a)						a
Ra-yi/Mustard			Giriraj Sarso (a)			Chhattisgarh Sarso (b)			a b
Tiwara			Bachali Haat (a)						a
Kulthi			Sarguja local (a)						a

Masoor			Desi (a)					a
Alsi			Local / Desi (a)					a

Characteristics Identified by Farmers for Trial's varieties

Crop	Serial No. of Identified Varieties	Identified Varieties	Type of varieties	Characteristics Identified by Farmers				
				Productivity (Serial No. of identified Variety)	Taste and Digestive (Serial No. of identified Variety)	Insect Resistance	Resistance/requirement	Grain size and any other
Black gram	1	Kheri	Local	--	--	--	--	
Rayi/Mustard	1	Giriraj Sarso	Improved	1>2	No data			
	2	Chhattisgarh Sarso	Improved					Small size seed rather than Giriraj
Tiwara	1	Bachali Haat	Local	--	--			
Kulthi	1	Sarguja	Local	--	--			
Masoor	1	Desi	Local	---				
Alsi	1	Desi	Local	--				

Reporting Month: March 2021:

Selection of appropriate varieties for Year 2021:

Showing date	T. F. No.	T.P. No.	Farmer's Trial plot name	Local/KVK variety name	Identified Farmer's Variety Name	Crop name	Seeds are appropriate for using in next year – YES/NO	Qt.* of Seed in Community Seed Bank
03/12/2020	-	--	Hareram	Local	Kheri	Black gram	Yes	
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Im-	Giriraj Sarso	Rayi/	Yes	

				proved		Mus-tard		
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Im-proved	Chhattis-garh Sarso	Mus-tard	Yes	
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Local	Bachali Haat	Tiwara	Yes	
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Local	Sarguja	Kulthi	Yes	
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Local	Desi	Masoor	Yes	
03/12/2020	--	--	Hareram	Local	Desi	Alsi	Yes	

- Total kg Pulses and oil seed received in Community Seed Bank for November sowing.

*- Total quantity represent the total seeds, which received from trial plots and passbook beneficiaries. The data were taken from community seed bank's ledger and passbook.

ANNEXURE-1

Chhattisgarh

Varietal Trial Plot Design for Monsoon Season: December 2020

Biodiversity: Oilseed and pulses' seeds for sowing in November-December 2020

VARIETAL TRIAL ON FRAMER'S FIELD

Seed Biodiversity: Total Crops: 6 and Total Verities: 7

	Chana/Bengal Gram	Rayi/ Mus-tard Black	Tiwara	Kulthi	Masoor	Linseed/Alsi
Farmer Verities	0	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)	0	Sarguja/ loca/ farmer sanjay markam / betgahna haat	Desi	Desi Farmer variety
Village Haat	Kheri Chana (Manoj/ Bahali Haat)	0	Local Bachali Haat/Salaram	0	0	0
Improved Seed	0	Chhattisgarh Sarso	0	0	0	0
Total	1	2	1	1	1	1

VARIETAL TRIAL ON FRAMER'S FIELD
(October-November)
Chhattisgarh

1.TRIAL FARM -1: RAMPAD MARKAM
Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur

Black Chana – Yellow Mustard (Sarso) Intercropping

No. of trial – 06

Total Dimension Intercropping- 37.5 sq. m

Total Dimension	<-----7.5 M X 5 M----->					
Plot Dimension	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>
Trial no.	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Mustard	Chana	Mustard	Chana	Mustard
Variety	Farmer	Farmer	Local	Farmer	Certified	Farmer
Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bahali Haat)	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bahali Haat)	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bahali Haat)	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)
Seed Quantity	100g	50g	100g	50g	100g	50g
Row to Row Distance	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	15 cm	10 cm	15 cm	10 cm	10 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

2.TRIAL FARM -2: RAMPAD MARKAM
Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur

KHESARI (TIWARA) - Black Chana – Yellow Mustard Intercropping

No. of trial – 07

Total Dimension Intercropping- 45 sq.

m

Total Dimension	<-----9 M X 5 M----->
-----------------	-----------------------

Plot Dimension	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M >	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M >	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M >	<1.5MX5 M>
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Tiwara	Mustard	Tiwara	Chana	Tiwara	Mustard
Variety	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer
Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Local Bachali Haat/Salar am	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)	Local Bachali Haat/Salar am	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Local Bachali Haat/Salar am	Girraj Sarso (Bhaisajhar Haat/Rampad Markam)
Seed Quantity	200g	100g	50g	100g	200g	100g	50g
Row to Row Distance	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	2 cm	15 cm	2 cm	10 cm	2 cm	15 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

3.TRIAL FARM -3: RAMPAD MARKAM Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur

HIRWA (Kulthi) – Black Chana – Masoor Intercropping:

No. of trial – 07

Total Dimension Intercropping- 45 sq. m

Total Dimension	-----9 M X 5 M----->						
Plot Dimension	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5 M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5 M>	<1.5MX5M>
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Kulthi	Chana	Masoor	Chana	Masoor	Kulthi
Variety	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer	Local	Farmer	Local	Farmer

Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Sarguja/loca/farmer sanjay mar-kam/betgahna haat	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Desi	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Desi	Sarguja/loca/farmer sanjay mar-kam/betgahna haat
Seed Quantity	200g	100g	200g	100g	200g	100g	100g
Row to Row Distance	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	30 cm
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	2 cm	10 cm	2 cm	10 cm	2 cm	2 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. Percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

4.TRIAL FARM -4: RAMPAD MARKAM Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur

**Black Chana – Yellow Mustard (Sarso) (University approved variety) Intercropping
No. of trial – 07 Total Dimension Intercropping- 45 sq. m**

Total Dimension	<-----9 M X 5 M----->						
Plot Dimension	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5 M>
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Sarso	Chana	Sarso	Chana	Sarso	Chana
Variety	Farmer	Approved	Farmer	Approved	Farmer	Approved	Farmer
Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Chhattisgarh Sarso	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Chhattisgarh Sarso	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Chhattisgarh Sarso	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)
Seed Quantity	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g
Row to Row	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm

Distance							
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	15 cm	10 cm	15 cm	10 cm	15 cm	10 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. Percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

**5.TRIAL FARM -5: RAMPAD MARKAM
Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur**

Black Chana – Masoor Intercropping

No. of Trial -6

Total Dimension	-----9 M X 5 M----->						
Plot Dimension	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5 M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5 M>	<1.5MX5 M>	<1MX5 M>	<1.5MX5 M>
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Masoor	Chana	Masoor	Chana	Masoor	Chana
Variety	Farmer	Local	Farmer	Local	Farmer	Local	Farmer
Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Desi	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Desi	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)	Desi	Kheri Chana (Manoj/Bachali Haat)
Seed Quantity	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g	100g
Row to Row Distance	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm	30 cm	45 cm
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	2 cm	10 cm	2 cm	10 cm	2 cm	10 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. Percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

**6.TRIAL FARM -6: RAMPAD MARKAM
Village: Bhaisajhar, Block- Kota, Bilaspur**

Linseed/Alsi – Black Chana Intercropping:

No. of Trial -6

Total Dimension	<-----7.5 M X 5 M----->					
Plot Dimension	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>	<1MX5M>	<1.5MX5M>
Trial no.	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6
Pattern	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop	Single crop
Crop	Chana	Linseed/Alsi	Chana	Linseed/Alsi	Chana	Linseed/Alsi
Variety	Farmer	Farmer	Local	Farmer	Farmer	Farmer
Variety Name	Kheri Chana (Manoj/ Bahali Haat)	Local Variety	Kheri Chana (Manoj/ Bahali Haat)	Local Variety	Kheri Chana (Manoj/ Bahali Haat)	Local Variety
Seed Quantity	100g	50g	100g	50g	100g	50g
Row to Row Distance	30 cm	30 cm	30 cm	30 cm	30 cm	30 cm
Plant to plant distance	10 cm	10 cm	10 cm	10 cm	10 cm	10 cm

The Trails are designed in such a way that the purity of the variety will be maintained without leaving soil, unsown. Percentage of the germination of seed will be tasted before sowing

ANNEXURE-3

Pre-approval on 3 December 2020 for seed distribution via passbook:

S. No.	Pulses	Variety	Total Wt.		No. of Beneficiaries
1	Black Chana	Kheri	10 kg		10
2	Masoor	--	--		--
3	Raye (black seed)	Local Giriraj	10 Kg		10
4	Tiwra	Local	10 kg		10
	Maha tiwara	Local	5 kg		5
5	Linseed/Tisi/Alsi	Local kiran	5 kg		5
6	Kulthi	Local surguja	5 kg		5
7	Baturi	Rachana variety	5 kg		5
		Total	50 kg		50

- Total direct beneficiary was50..... in November-December 2020 sowing period.
- Total new passbook distributed in ...50..... November- December 2020 sowing season.
- Total50..... Kg seed distributed in November-December 2020 sowing season.

ANNEXURE _3

Beneficiaries:

Total Beneficiaries	60 Direct and 120 Indirect
Area Covered	15 Acre
Passbook Distributed	60
Updated on	31 March 2021

----- Direct Beneficiaries List -----

Image:1, Seed Saving Account number 1 to 16; image provided by state coordinator

ACCOUNT OPENING FORM TO OPEN SEED ACCOUNT			
क्र.सं.	नाम	पता/घर नं. ग्राम	जिला कोड
1	गुलाब सिंह	श्री कलीशर	भंडावा 495113-01-0001
2	बलराज सिंह	श्री परदेवी	--- 495113-01-0002
3	वेशा कुमार	श्री खाना	--- 495113-01-0003
4	सरबत सिंह	श्री मिठुआ	--- 495113-01-0004
5	जवाहर प्रसाद	श्री जयपुर	--- 495113-01-0005
6	श्रीमती सरनबाई	श्री फेरुआ	--- 495113-01-0006
7	रामचंद्र मल्ल	श्री लक्ष्मण	495113-01-0007
8	दुर्गेश कुमार	श्री गुलाबी	495113-01-0008
9	कुंदर सिंह	श्री जलडिह	495113-01-0009
10	शुभेन्द्र कुमार	सरखाना	495113-01-0010
11	शुभेन्द्र कुमार	भान सिंह	495113-01-0011
12	रमजय कुमार	श्री वाराण	495113-01-0012
13	शशि शर	भरत सिंह	495113-01-0013
14	गिरधर	माखन	495113-01-0014
15	गिरधर	रामशरण	495113-01-0015
16	सुखपाल सिंह	रामदीन	495113-01-0016

Image:2, Seed Saving Account number 17 to 32; image provided by state coordinator

क्र.सं.	नाम	पति/पत्नी	ग्राम	खाता सं.	सं.
17	शमभद्र			495113-01-00017	33
18	शमभद्र			495113-01-00018	34
19	मनोज कुमार	मान सिंह		495113-01-00019	35
20	शुभेला	दशरथ सिंह		495113-01-00020	36
21	शमभद्र	हरचंद सिंह		495113-01-00021	37
22	विश्वनाथ	मनिराज सिंह		495113-01-00022	38
23	महावीर			495113-01-00023	39
24	गोपी राज	आडू राज		495113-01-00024	40
25	राज मेहराज	हरचंद		495113-01-00025	41
26	श्याम सिंह	हरचंद		495113-01-00026	42
27	कमल सिंह	धान सिंह		495113-01-00027	43
28	हरि सिंह	भरत सिंह		495113-01-00028	44
29	दिलेश कुमार			495113-01-00029	45
30	शुशील कुमार	राज सिंह		495113-01-00030	46
31	गोवर्धन	सुरज सिंह		495113-01-00031	47
32	दीप राज	मनिराज		495113-01-00032	48

Image:3, Seed Saving Account number 33 to 48; image provided by state coordinator

क्र.सं.	नाम	पता	मंडल	अकाउंट नंबर
33	शरद सिंह	कलेरा	भैरवा	495113-01-00033
34	भागवत सिंह	अमरनाथ	-	495113-01-00034
35	अश्वनी कुमार	श्यामसिंह	-	495113-01-00035
36	परमानंद	खिहारी	-	495113-01-00036
37	श्यामसिंह नेदी	परदेशीराज	-	495113-00037
38	श्रीधर ठाकुर	बी रतिका	-	495113-01-00038
39	अनिल ठाकुर	समुद्र सिंह	-	495113-01-00039
40	प्रेम ठाकुर	शिवगोला	-	495113-01-00040
41	अशोक कुमार	श्यामसिंह	-	495113-01-00041
42	भगवानदीव SC	गोरेखाल SC	-	495113-01-00042
43	रामाबाळबाई	रामडी SC	-	495113-01-00043
44	कुलकर्णी	गोपाल	-	495113-01-00044
45	विभाजित जागस	डांग-नावा	-	495113-01-00045
46	डांगेन्यु कमा	मान सिंह	-	495113-01-00046
47	शंका सिंह	शिवराज	-	495113-01-00047
48	गोरेखाल SC	वंकटाराज	-	495113-01-00048

Image:4, Seed Saving Account number 49 to 60; image provided by state coordinator

Sl. No.	Name	Address	Phone No.	Account No.
49	सुभाष चंद्र	महाराष्ट्र जिल्हा	मोबा. 98201	425113-01-00049
50	रमेश सिंह	धनसिंग	-	425113-01-00050
51	दीपक कुमार	शंभुनगर	-	425113-01-00051
52	यशपाल	धनसिंग	-	425113-01-00052
53	पवन कुमार	फांफुवा	-	425113-01-00053
54	राजेश कुमार	दरभय	-	425113-01-00054
55	सुनिल कुमार	धनसिंग	-	425113-01-00055
56	जिणेरी	सेरुवा	-	425113-01-00056
57	अदिभान	गौडा	-	425113-01-00057
58	चतुर सिंह	दिरकुवा	-	425113-01-00058
59	सुदेश कुमार	शंभुनगर	-	425113-01-00059
60	श्रीराम सुवाला	गोडा	-	425113-01-00060